

THE ECONOMICS OF ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOLS IN ADINUGRAHA'S PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Islamic Boarding Schools are currently experiencing a special shift related to the world of work. Currently, the development of entrepreneurship in the pesantren environment has become a necessity, especially if it is associated with pesantren education which emphasizes independence, hard work, discipline and honesty that supports the entrepreneurial spirit. This article intends to study and describe Hendri Hermawan's thoughts on Islamic Boarding School Economics. The approach used is a literature review whose primary sources come from his works and also from other journals that have discussion topics that are in accordance with this research. The findings of this study show his thoughts on the Economics of Islamic Boarding Schools, namely 1) It is necessary to develop the potential of Islamic Boarding Schools so that later they can be useful for many people both inside and outside the Islamic Boarding School. 2) It is necessary to conduct entrepreneurship training for the students, this is done with the aim that later after graduating from the Islamic Boarding School the students have the provisions to enter the world of work or when they want to open their own business. This entrepreneurship training aims to create entrepreneurs and grow creative economic businesses towards the economic independence of the people.

Keywords: Islamic Boarding School, Entrepreneurship, Islamic Boarding School

1. Introduction

Based on the results of research from the Research and Development Center (Puslitbang) for Religious and Religious Education of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia in 2005, which said that the flow of globalization gave color to the world of Islamic boarding schools caused by the tendency of global co-optation to marginalize. faced with several choices, either to be reactive or to play an active role (Chusmeru et al., 2017). The existence of Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia is not only synonymous with the meaning of Islam as we know it, but also contains the meaning of Indonesian authenticity.

Historically, the development of Islamic boarding schools began with trade, then developed and penetrated the education sector and Islamic da'wah, and ended with power. Power was formed only to be a tool in securing and developing the economic sector with the education sector. The relationship between economy, education and politics is what creates the tradition and order of the Muslim archipelago. The better the economic status, the quality of education, and the wider the influence of its power, the more erudite the culture and traditions that are born and developed, including Islamic boarding schools (Tirta, 2017).

According to Hamzah (2022) Pesantren is a religious institution that cannot be separated from the community, especially rural communities, because pesantren grows and develops from and for the community. Hamzah (2022) emphasized that Islamic boarding schools have a very strategic role, namely as a center for religious, educational, social and cultural development as well as an economic strength. Thus, Islamic boarding schools become an important part in the development of educational institutions both social and economic as well as religious and moral that are able to face challenges in an increasingly developing era.

However, in reality, many economic potentials have not been explored properly. There are not many pesantren that run intra-pesantren business activities to improve the welfare of the institution and also the caregivers in it. In addition, there are Islamic boarding schools that have not empowered their students and have left them to outsiders to take over the management of several economic fields that can be empowered by the pesantren themselves. Some pesantren do not empower this potential, where the business within the pesantren is only managed by a few groups, so the scope is not broad and comprehensive to various economic fields and the benefits cannot be said to fully touch the welfare of the institution or the occupants in it (Zuhirsyan, 2018).

Islamic boarding school, one of the institutions that has the potential to move towards a people-based economy, as it has the power. If Ponpes (Islamic boarding schools) are only spectators in the future era, other micro-economic institutions will move towards progress. Therefore, a careful analysis is needed so that this potential can be developed and can be useful for many parties (Toha, 2018). For this reason, Islamic boarding schools need a forum for students to develop their Lifeskills and talents so that they can be trained and continue to be developed.

If the Islamic Boarding School has fulfilled its three main functions, namely First, as a center for cadre of religious thinkers (center of excellence). Second, as an institution that prints human resources (human resources). Third, as an institution that empowers the community (agent of development). So the Islamic Boarding School is a positive consumer and is supported by the surrounding community. This means that students and the surrounding community are basically consumers whose needs can be met economically by the pesantren itself. So, pesantren can essentially be independent to become the center of economic institutions, for their citizens

inside and outside the pesantren (Muh. Fahri 2017). Therefore, it is necessary to have business training for students (Santripreneur), so that the potential and interests of the students can be developed according to their fields.

Santripreneur has the meaning of people who study in Islamic boarding schools, students who have their own business and dare to open independent productive activities. It can also be interpreted as a student who is brave in taking risks to run a business by taking advantage of opportunities to create new businesses with innovative approaches so that the managed businesses develop to be large and independent in facing the challenges of competition (Siti, 2018). Thus, what is meant by santri entrepreneurship education is a conscious and planned effort carried out by Islamic boarding schools in increasing the independence of students. So it is hoped that in the future, the students will have the provisions to start a business.

Economics for an institution such as a boarding school is the heart of life for the progress of both the education system and the existence of other fields. Research result Syafar (2016). Explained that Islamic boarding schools as educational institutions have roles and functions in carrying out academic and non-academic tasks, so that they are able to form students who have the capacity and capability to strengthen their competence in terms of cognitive, affective and psychomotor which are directly beneficial to local residents. The interactionist-cultural relationship between Islamic Boarding Schools and the community makes the existence and presence of Islamic boarding schools stronger in community change and empowerment (Tirta, 2017).

On this basis, it means that Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia must return to their role, becoming the main pawn in the role of driving the economy through their independence. As well as applicable management of pesantren so that there is harmony between educational development and

economic development. Because without a strong economy, Islamic boarding schools will experience setbacks and even lose their existence. Recorded more than 5,000 Islamic boarding schools spread over 68,000 villages, is evidence in itself to state that Islamic boarding schools are an institution that has a unique culture. And this is also proof that pesantren can be said to be a subculture. It is also unique, which in turn can generate enormous economic value if managed professionally (Ahmad, 2005).

2. Research Methodology

This research uses a literature review approach whose primary sources come from the works of Hendri Hermawan and various other sources such as articles, scientific journals or others relevant to the topic of this research. From the collected data, it was analyzed using a descriptive approach in order to get a complete picture of the research object.

3. Results and Discussion

Hendri Hermawan's Biography

Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha is a PNS lecturer at IAIN Pekalongan (2019-present). He was born in Serang, March 11, 1987, he started his teaching career since graduating from Master of Islamic Studies (Islamic Economics Concentration) at UII Yogyakarta, by being a permanent lecturer at UDINUS Semarang for 8 years. His doctoral education (S3) took the concentration of Halal Management at UIN Walisongo Semarang (2017-2020). Apart from being a lecturer, he is also active in writing books, national and international scientific journals with the theme of Islamic economics and Islamic studies.

Hendri Hermawan's Works On Islamic Boarding School Economic Research

No	Research title	Finding
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1	(Adinugraha et al., 2020) Santripreneur Improvement in Students of Pondok Pesantren Uswatun Hasanah for Become Entrepreneurs	Hendi Hermawan conducts entrepreneurial mentoring activities for students of the Uswatun Khasanah Islamic Boarding School Semarang, this activity is carried out with the aim of increasing knowledge and understanding for students of the Uswatun Hasanah Islamic Boarding School Semarang about entrepreneurship, helping the students of the Uswatun Hasanah Islamic Boarding School in order to open the mindset to become entrepreneurs and can help explore ideas for entrepreneurship
2	(Adinugraha et al., 2022) Assistance in Enhancing Entrepreneurial Capability for Bustanul Mansuriyah Islamic Boarding School Students	Hendri Hermawan conducts entrepreneurial mentoring activities for the students of the Bustanul Mansuriyah Islamic Boarding School, this entrepreneurial mentoring activity aims to expand students' knowledge and awareness about entrepreneurship at the Bustanul Mansuriyah Islamic Boarding School, and help them open their minds to the possibility of becoming entrepreneurs. The implementation of this service uses an educational approach, socialization, and entrepreneurship training to open an entrepreneurial attitude from an early age, thus enabling students to achieve economic independence. As a result of the adoption of this service, the majority of students at the Bustanul Mansuriyah Islamic Boarding School are able to understand and practice digital marketing, as well as create simple business plans in groups that are run in their various businesses. The suggestion from this service is that all students in Indonesia from an early age must be educated, socialized, and guided as Santripreneurs so that they are able to be economically independent and create jobs for themselves and society in general.
3	(Muhamad Rozaidin dan Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha, 2020) Application of Accounting for Islamic Boarding Schools (Study on Al Hasyimi Islamic Boarding School Cooperative, Pekalongan Regency)	Applicable Accounting Standards. This research activity was carried out with the aim of examining how the application of applicable accounting and its conformity with accounting standards in the Al Hasyimi Islamic boarding school cooperative and to find out the importance of accounting for an institution.

Similar Research on Islamic Boarding School Economics

4	<p>(Hariyanto, 2017) Fostering Entrepreneurial Spirit Towards Economic Independence of People Based on Islamic Boarding Schools (Case Study at PP Darul Ulum Banyuanyar Pamekasan)</p>	<p>Hariyanto conducted research on how to foster an entrepreneurial spirit for students at Darul Ulum Islamic Boarding School Banyuanyar Pamekasan. The results of the study: 1) Darul Ulum Islamic Boarding School Banyuanyar Pamekasan in cultivating an entrepreneurial spirit among its students by implementing the vision of the Islamic Boarding School which is to give birth to a generation of Muslims with good morals, knowledge of practice and scientific deeds. In practice, students are given the freedom to carry out activities that support the achievement of this vision as long as it provides benefits to themselves and others. 2) Creative businesses run by students and alumni of Darul Ulum Islamic Boarding School Banyuanyar Pamekasan include shops, businesses to produce goods, services and finance sectors. Entrepreneurial activities in the shopping sector include household to local segmentation around Islamic boarding schools. Goods production activities include the production of drinking water in Nuri bottles, the production of ice cubes, the production of snacks, and the production of handicrafts. Meanwhile, in the service sector, it includes photocopying, typing and binding. And financial activities in the form of the establishment of BMT Nuri which already has 16 branches. 3) Darul Ulum Islamic Boarding School Banyuanyar Pamekasan educates self-reliance in all fields including economic independence. Efforts for this are carried out by participating in running the business while being a student and doing their own activities after entering the community.</p>
5	<p>(Suyatman, 2017) Islamic Boarding Schools and the Economic Independence of the Santri (Case of the Fathiyyah Al-Idrisiyyah Islamic Boarding School in Tasikmalaya)</p>	<p>Suyatman conducted research on Islamic boarding schools and economic independence in the Fathiyyah Al-Idrisiyyah Islamic Boarding School Tasikmalaya. The results of this research are: 1) The teachings of the tarekat and Islamic religious values in general which</p>

		<p>are taught to students and congregations are the basis of values in businesses in the economic field developed by Sufi entrepreneurs. Spirit personality, straight intentions and great vision and mission are not only used as material for the appreciation of religious spirituality, but are also internalized in the business practices that are carried out, and are used as motivation and spirit of strength in every form of action and decision making. 2) The paradigm of the mechanism and at the same time the organism is the paradigm of Islamic education developed at Ponpes Fadris. These two paradigms view that worldly material aspects and religious spirituality values are not dichotomous aspects of life, but are a unity in building a prosperous life in this world and the hereafter. 3) The contribution of Ponpes Fadris to the development of the surrounding community, or its congregation in general spread across several regions of the archipelago, is not only limited to fulfilling the needs of ukhrawiyyah, but also includes services for the community in terms of worldly interests. This effort is carried out by developing and increasing the volume of business carried out with community participation in the process and enjoying the results</p>
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The contribution of Hendri Hermawan's Islamic boarding school thought

The rationalization of Hendri Hermawan's thoughts on Islamic Boarding School Economics in particular is in fostering an entrepreneurial spirit in the students at Islamic Boarding Schools. This needs to be done because, through activities to develop the potential of each Islamic boarding school, it will provide benefits for many people, both inside and outside the pesantren itself, besides that it is necessary to conduct entrepreneurship training to the santri so that later when they have graduated from pesantren education, they are not only have the provision of religious knowledge but

also the knowledge of entrepreneurship. This is motivated by technological advances that are developing rapidly, in which religious educational institutions are very less attractive. Therefore, Islamic boarding schools as religious educational institutions are required to be able to compete with formal education in order to overcome the decline of religious values and the decline of morals and morals in children in the current era (Firman, 2021).

Currently, Islamic boarding schools have undergone many changes, this is due to the development of science and technology, as well as community demands and government policies related to the education system. Pesantren is the root of independence education in Indonesia. Pesantren itself is the oldest educational institution today and is considered a product of indigenous Indonesian culture. Potentially these characteristics have a large enough opportunity to be used as a basis for addressing globalization and other problems facing pesantren, in particular, and the wider community in general, such as independence, hard work, sincerity and simplicity (Muh. Hamzah, 2022).

From the research conducted by Hendri Hermawan, he explained that it is necessary to develop the potential of Islamic boarding schools and also provide entrepreneurship training assistance. This will be beneficial for students who after graduating from Islamic boarding schools, because they are not only equipped with religious knowledge but also entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship education is defined as the education of prospective entrepreneurs to have the courage, independence, and skills so as to minimize failure in business. With an emphasis on skills or skills, in entrepreneurship education, an educational model is needed that enlarges the portion of practice compared to the theories being taught. The practice given to students must accommodate actual examples in the field to realize the formation of entrepreneurial character (Suyatman, 2017).

4. Simpulan

The findings of this study show Hendri Hermawan's thoughts on Islamic boarding school economics which focus on developing potential and providing mentoring as well as entrepreneurship training. These results are 1) It is necessary to develop the potential of Islamic boarding schools so that later they can be useful for many people both inside and outside the boarding school. 2) It is necessary to conduct entrepreneurship training for the students, this is done with the aim that later after graduating from the Islamic Boarding School the students have the provisions to enter the world of work or when they want to open their own business. This entrepreneurship training aims to create entrepreneurs and grow creative economic businesses towards the economic independence of the people.

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